

MEASURING COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITES BY FLEXURAL TESTS

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Background

- Compressive strength is a key limitation for composite structures
- Typically significantly lower than tensile strength
- Open hole compressive strength and Compression After Impact (CAI) are design drivers
- Very difficult to measure compressive strength accurately
- Low values and high variability in many tests

Ueda, 2023

Variations in reported strength of UD IM7/8552

□ Diverse results from key experiments

Example: fibre compressive strength of IM7/8552 composites

More than
factor of 2
difference!

Hao Cui, Cranfield,
NWPU Suzhou

Compression testing

- Load introduction causes stress concentrations
- Shear stresses present, which reduce strength
- Normally get premature failure at grips
- Gauge section failures usually associated with buckling or defects

Compressive stress

Interlaminar shear stress

Lee & Soutis, 2007

Flexural testing

- Simple test and specimen preparation
- Four-point bending can produce compressive failure away from stress concentrations
- Pin-ended buckling tests completely eliminate stress concentrations and can give much higher failure strains
- BUT may overestimate the failure strain due to the effect of the strain gradient

Effect of strain gradient

- Scaled tests on T800/924 carbon-epoxy showed a strong effect of thickness
- Failure is due to shear instability at the micromechanical level
- With strain gradient, less stressed fibres support others, increasing failure strain

Wisnom, Atkinson and Jones, 1997

Overview

- Avoiding roller failure in bending tests
- Sandwich beam tests
- Evaluating the effect of strain gradient
- Measuring pseudo-ductile stress-strain response in compression using a bending test

Four-point bending

- ASTM D6272, span-to-thickness ratio 32:1
- Rubber pads under loading noses
- Standard loading nose diameter $D=10$ mm
 - Failed in compression, significant variability
 - 4 / 5 specimens failed at loading point
- Repeated with loading nose $D=25$ mm
 - 10 specimens all failed in gauge section
 - 18% higher strain at failure

D=10mm: Failure at loading noses

D=25mm: Failure in the gauge section

Loading nose D (mm)	Strain at failure(%) (CV)	No of samples
10	-1.19 (13.2%)	5
25	-1.41 (7.5%)	10

Wu & Wisnom, 2023

Avoiding strain gradient

- Sandwich beam with deep core
- Honeycomb can be used
- Relatively low shear strength
- Wood much stronger, easier to machine
- PMMA is alternative
- Skins bonded with epoxy

Sandwich beams – effect of strain gradient

- Vary depth of the beam to change strain gradient
- Keep gauge section dimensions the same
- Increase span to limit loading forces

Results - effect of strain gradient

- IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy skins, $t = 0.5$ mm
- Core t from 6 mm to 38 mm
- Little effect of strain gradient above 10 mm thickness
- 1.36% strain for 38 mm core
- 14% greater than 1.19%, highest reported in direct compression (Thomson et al, 2019)

Pseudo-ductile composites

- Thin-ply carbon/epoxy angle-ply with central 0s

$[\pm 27_7/0]_s$

Standard modulus High modulus

- Pseudo-ductile response in tension:

Fragmentation of UD plies

Dispersed delamination

Angle plies failure

Edge view

- What happens in compression?

Wu, Fuller, Wisnom, 2020

Sandwich beam - test setup

Results – surface strains against moment

Sandwich beam set up

Results – stress evaluation

- Know moment from load and geometry
- Work out neutral axis position from strains based on linear strain variation
- Neglect contribution of core
- Load in tensile skin from strain and modulus
- Hence can calculate stress in compression skin

Neutral axis shifts relative to lower surface of the bottom skin

Stress-strain behaviour

- Pseudo-ductility in compression
- Nonlinear response with knee point
- Pseudo-ductile strain ε_d of 0.41%
- Fragmentation in 0° plies

Ply fragmentation

Investigation of Compressive Behavior of Glass/Carbon Fibre Hybrid Composite with 4-point Flexural Test

Aree Tongloet

10.40 on Thursday, 3 August 2023

Hall 2A, Understanding & Improving
Longitudinal Compressive Strength –
Session 8

Conclusions

- Flexural tests can be used effectively to measure compressive response
- Need large rollers to avoid local failure
- Strain gradient effects have been quantitatively measured - no strain gradient effect with deep sandwich beam
- Compressive pseudo-ductile stress-strain behaviour was demonstrated in thin-ply $[\pm 27_7/0]_s$ laminates from flexural tests

References

- D. Thomson, H. Cui, B. Erice and N. Petrinic “*A study on the longitudinal compression strength of fibre reinforced composites under uniaxial and off-axis loads using cross-ply laminate specimens*”. Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf, Vol. 121, pp 213–22, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2019.03.034>
- M. R. Wisnom, J. A. Atkinson, and M. I. Jones “*Reduction in compressive strain to failure with increasing specimen size in pin-ended buckling tests*”. Compos Science Techn, Vol. 57, pp 1303-1308, 1997. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538\(97\)00057-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(97)00057-2)
- X. Wu and M. R. Wisnom, “*Compressive failure strain of unidirectional carbon fibre composites from bending tests*”. Composite Structures, Vol. 304, 116467, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2022.116467>
- X. Wu, J. D. Fuller and M. R. Wisnom “*Role of fibre fragmentation on pseudo-ductility of thin-ply $[\pm 27_{\text{r}}/0]_s$ carbon fibre laminates with high modulus 0° plies under compressive and flexural loading*”. Composites Science and Technology Vol. 199, 108377, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2020.108377>
- M. R. Wisnom, “*Effect of Shear Stresses in Indirect Compression Tests on Unidirectional Carbon Fibre-Epoxy* », AIAA Journal, Vol. 29, pp 1692-7, 1991. <https://doi.org/10.2514/3.10792>
- J. Lee, C. Soutis “*A study on the compressive strength of thick carbon fibre–epoxy laminates*” Compos Science Techn, Vol. 67, 2015-2026, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2006.12.001>

Thank you

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